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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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DORIVOR O‘SIMLIKLARNI KLONAL MIKROKO‘PAYTIRISH

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Annotatsiya: Hujayra va to‘qimalar kulturasi sohasida erishilgan yutuqlar asosida o‘simliklarni vegetativ ko‘paytirishning yangi usuli – klonli mikroko‘paytirish (in vitro sharoitida (probirkada) o‘simliklarni jinsiz ko‘payishi, dastlabki nusxasi bilan genetik bir xil) usuli yaratildi. Usul asosida o‘simlik hujayrasining faqat o‘ziga xos bo‘lgan totipotentlikni amalga oshirishdek ajoyib xususiyat yotadi, ya’ni ekzogen omillar ta’sirida o‘simlik organizmi paydo boladi. Bu usul asosida o‘simlik hujayralarigagina xos bo‘lgan noyob xususiyat, totipotentlik xususiyati, ya’ni tashqaridan keladigan ta’sir orqali butun o‘simlik organizmi hosil bo‘lishiga turtki bo‘lishi yotadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: In vitro, mikroklonal, eksplant, gastrit, ginkgo biloba, plantatsiya, *Hippophae rhamnoides L*

Hozirgi vaqtda dorivor o‘simliklarni in vitro ko‘paytirish, hujayra kulturasi, mikroklonal ko‘paytirishga katta e’tibor berilmoqda. Bu yo‘nalishdagi tadqiqotlar dunyoning rivojlangan davlatlarining ko‘plab laboratoriyalarida olib borilmoqda. Shuningdek, O‘zbekistonda farmatsevtika ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirish, mahalliy xomashyo asosida dori vositalari texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish va bu ishlarni hayotga tatbiq etish bugungi kunda davlatimiz rahbarining muhim vazifalaridan biri sifatida qaralmoqda. Xususan, O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti kimyo fakulteti biotexnologiya ilmiy laboratoriyasida kartoshkani klonal mikroko‘paytirish usullari orqali kasalliklarga, issiqqa, sho‘rlanishga chidamli navlarini yaratish bo‘yicha ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda.

Mikroko‘paytirishdan foydalanish doirasi juda keng bo‘lib, kundan kunga yanada oshib bormoqda. Eng avvalo in vitro sharoitida o‘simliklarni yog‘ochli turlarini, nina bargli va ayniqsa, yo‘qolib ketayotgan o‘simliklar hamda dorivor o‘simliklarni ko‘paytirish maqsadida bu usuldan foydalanish katta samara berishi isbotlangan. Keyingi yillarda respublikamizda dorivor o‘simliklarni muhofaza qilish, tabiiy resurslardan oqilona foydalanish, dorivor o‘simliklar plantatsiyalari barpo etish va ularni qayta ishlash borasida izchil islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Ammo ba’zi istiqbolli o‘simliklar sonining kamligi va ularning tabiiy ko‘payishi qiyinligi sababli plantatsiyalarni yaratish va ko‘paytirishda muammolar mavjud. Bu muammolarni bartaraf etish maqsadida Farg‘ona davlat universiteti professor-o‘qituvchilari va magistrleri tomonidan bir qancha foydali o‘simliklarni mikroklonal ko‘paytirish yo‘nalishida ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda. Xususan, manzarali va mevali o‘simliklardan ginkgo biloba va chakanda (*Hippophae rhamnoides L*)ning

biologik xossalari o'rganilib, in vitro sharoitda ularni mikroklonal ko'paytirish bo'yicha dastlabki ishlar olib borilmoqda. Etnobotanik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, chakanda o'simligi gastrit, gepatit, bronxitni davolashda ham qo'llaniladi. Bu o'simlikning tabiiy zaxiralaridan tejamkorlik bilan foydalanish, uning cheklangan maydonlarini muhofaza qilish va ko'paytirish chora-tadbirlari bilan shug'ullanish zarur. Chakanda ikki qavatli o'simlik bo'lganligi sababli, ekishdan oldin erkak va urg'ochisini aniqlash qiyin. Ko'pincha, dalalarga ekilganida, ko'plab erkak o'simliklar mavjud va buning natijasida hosildorlik pasayadi. Buning oldini olish uchun maqsad o'simliklarni mikroklonal ko'paytirish bilan ekish va yuqori hosil olish mumkin. Klonal mikroko'paytirish jarayonini to'rt bosqichga bo'lish mumkin:

birinchi – donor o'simlikni tanlash, eksplantlarni ajratish va yaxshi o'sadigan steril kultura olish;

ikkinchi – mikroko'paytirishni o'zi, meriklonlarni eng ko'p (maksimal) miqdorini olishga erishilgan davrni va sharoitni tanlash;

uchinchi – ko'paytirilgan navdani ildiz olishi va ularni tuproq sharoitiga moslashtirish, kerak bo'lganda regenerant – o'simliklarni sovuq haroratda saqlash;

to'rtinchi – o'simlikni issiqxona sharoitida o'stirish va ularni maydonga chiqarib ekish yoki sotishga tayyorlash.

Ma'lumki, ginkgo biloba va chakanda o'simliklari sekin o'sadi, ularning urug'ining unib chiqishi past, zararkunandalar va yuqori harorat ta'sirida zararlanishi tez-tez uchraydi, bu o'simliklarning mikroksion ko'payishi o'sish fazasini qisqartirish va kasalliklarga chidamli virussiz o'simliklar olish imkonini beradi.

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib aytish mumkinki, in vitro sharoitda o'simliklarning barglari, poyalari, kurtaklari va boshqa vegetativ organlaridan mikroklonal ko'paytirish katta iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega. Albatta, bu usulni boshqa an'anaviy usullardan ustunlik tomonlari juda ham ko'p, eng avvalo bu ustunliklar, genetik bir xil ekuv materialining olinishi, meristema to'qimalari kulturalari ishlatilishi hisobiga o'simliklarni virusli va boshqa yuqumli kasalliklardan holi bo'lishi, ko'payish koeffitsientining yuqoriligi (o'tchil va gulli o'simliklar uchun 104-105; ninabargli o'simliklar uchun –104), o'simlik rivojlanishshini yuvenil davrdan reproduktiv fazaga o'tishini tezlashishi, an'anaviy yo'llar bilan qiyin ko'payadigan o'simliklarni ko'paytirish, ishni yil davomida tashkil etish imkoniyatlarining mavjudligi va ko'chat materiallari o'stirish uchun kerak bo'lgan maydonni tejash, o'stirish jarayonini avtomatlashtirish imkoniyatlari va boshqalar.

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